

ISic1025

I.Sicily inscription 1025

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140504

1. Διονύσου καὶ Σ [— — — —]
2. ἱερατεύοντος [τοῦ δεῖνα τοῦ]
3. Ἀρίστωνος Θεο [— — —ς]
4. ΚΑΛΛΙΓΕΝΙΑΝΚΑΚΤ[— — — —]
5. εὐχὰν [ἀνέθηκε].
6. ²versus 4 recentior non ad titulum pertinens²
- 7.

Edition: PHI175421

1. Διονύσου καὶ Σ [εμέλας]
2. ἱερατεύοντος [τοῦ δεῖνα τοῦ]
3. Ἀρίστωνος, Θεο [— — —ς]
4. Καλλιγένιαν Καστ[— — —]
5. εὐχὰν [ἀνέθηκε].
6. ²vs. 4 recentior, non ad titulum pertinens (Kaibel)²
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492653

EDCS 39102179

PHI 140504

PHI 175421

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0205 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. *Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi*. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.11

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